

The ingenuity of biosphere citizens in light of international interactions: A boon for environmental peace and security diplomacy

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Abstract

The foundation of life on Earth today is the pervasive understanding of global citizens about environmental conservation within the framework of formal and informal discourses. In this process, constructive interactions between governments, nations, and international organizations contribute to the identity of international law subjects regarding environmental protection and support becoming more evident. This process can be realized based on the principle of awareness and information dissemination, the principle of transparency, and the principle of participation. This research aims to emphasize the consolidation of the global community's attitude towards peace-making and environmental security. The present research, which is based on library studies, seeks to answer the question of how much the ingenuity of Earth's inhabitants in protecting the environment depends on international interactions. The findings of the authors show that the preservation of the ecosystem is only possible through international cooperation and interactions, and this path requires strengthening treaty-based mechanisms and tools. Therefore, it seems that a high percentage of the ingenuity of citizens in protecting the inhabited Earth depends on factors such as the realization of treaty-based principles including the principle of participation, the principle of awareness and the principle of notification, and the realization of effective non-treaty-based tools such as crowd-sourcing and peace-making.

Keywords: Environmental diplomacy, environmental security, crowdsourcing, international relations

Introduction

The inhabited biosphere is the ground for the growth of plant and animal diversity and the habitat of the human species and the basis of the natural environment. Throughout different periods, the biosphere has undergone various transformations, some of which have inevitably led to threats that have emerged on a not-so-large scale, and ignoring them has caused accidents. Tampering with the fabric of the biosphere has caused the natural environment to react, and the environment of living beings now faces a serious threat. In this context, and despite environmental changes and the threats arisen, environmental security and, in turn, green peace face serious threats. The scope of these threats has become so wide that it has prompted the international community to take action. In fact, the history of the reactions traces back to the Stockholm Conference in 1972 and the Rio Summit in 1992. The international community, and governments in particular, became well aware that these threats not only lead to the destruction and devastation of the environment but also pose a serious challenge to security and peace. These factors led to serious consideration of environmental issues at regional and international summits. In this context, in order to maintain security and achieve peace, countries have decided to use their power and access to new technologies to peacefully mitigate these threats. In addition, countries have considered the role of negotiations and strengthening the peaceful discourse in order to maintain their position at the international level. The issue that forced governments to react was the acceptance of the role of the general public in protecting the environment. This led to the consideration of treaty and non-treaty dimensions in relation to the level of ingenuity and development of citizens. This is because it has provided a ground for strengthening diplomacy and has

taken into account peace-building approaches. In the present research, considering the importance of environmental diplomacy and commitment to international obligations, we will examine the issue of the ingenuity of biosphere citizens in the light of international interactions; an outcome for environmental peace and security diplomacy.

Treaty Discourse

Treaty mechanisms are in fact tools that are directly and transparently mentioned in treaties, or treaties are used to achieve them and have a two-way relationship with them. This is very important for environmental protection and can be presented in three titles

Table 1

Quantitative Approaches (Soft Law & Hard Law)	Qualitative Approaches	Effective Approaches
Stockholm Declaration, Rio Declaration, CITES Declaration, Convention on the Law of the Seas ^[1]	Principles of Sovereignty, Cooperation, Environmental Protection, Notification, Precaution, Cooperation and Assistance in Emergency Situations, Polluter Pays Principle, Participation of Private Individuals and Concepts such as Common Heritage of Humankind, Public Interest of Humankind, Rights of Future Generations, Sustainable Development, Common but Differentiated Responsibilities ^[2]	Reliable judicial procedures such as the Corfu case, Trail Smelter case, Nagymaros case ^[3]

These solutions, strategies, and approaches can greatly help in modeling environmental protection within the framework of international environmental law rules. Therefore, based

on international commitments and the level of adherence to them, interactions within the framework of environmental diplomacy are organized. This formal process greatly helps the growth of biosphere inhabitants towards demand. In fact, it is this demand that highlights the role of citizens and causes countries to involve them in environmental decision-making. We must be aware of the fact that today, diplomacy is not only between heads of state and political figures. Rather, diplomacy is a comprehensive framework that underpins all platforms for dialogue and negotiation. Therefore, the existing chapters in the context of treaties show the recognition of civil and non-governmental institutions and also individuals. The treaty structure, which is rooted in diplomacy, as a reliable and universal tool, has forward-moving effects ^[4]

Table 2

Treaty Structure	Executive Principles	Effectiveness
Aarhus Convention	Principle of Participation Principle of Awareness	Advocacy and claims of private real stakeholders
Framework Convention on Climate Change	The Principles of Cooperation, Environmental Protection, Precaution, Prevention, Common but Differentiated Responsibilities and the Concept of Intergenerational Equity	Biannual commitments of countries to reduce greenhouse gas emissions
Basel Convention	The Principles of Cooperation, Environmental Protection, Notification, Precaution, Prevention, Cooperation and Assistance in Emergency Situations, Polluter Pays	States' obligations to transboundary movement and disposal of waste

Green Security and Defensive Diplomacy

Defensive diplomacy is a universal approach that considers the general practices of governments within the international and diplomatic spheres. It plays an active role in guiding both official and unofficial diplomacy. Defensive diplomacy took on its fundamental form within the framework of modern strategic thinking. The integration of "diplomacy" as the primary tool of foreign policy and "defense" as the primary tool of defense policy became possible when the boundaries and limitations of these two entities were implicitly defined. This issue, in fact, shaped the initial concept of defensive diplomacy, which was only given attention in times of political deadlock. ^[5]

However, it seems that defensive diplomacy has gone beyond this and, beyond all discussions, has put on the agenda attention to international and regional interactions, peripheral issues such as environmental hazards, economic crises and political changes. The main argument in this diplomacy is that in cases where there are differences between two or more countries, these think tanks play an important role in familiarizing the parties to the dispute with each other and establishing direct relations between them by inviting the parties to the dispute or different ideological and political tendencies to dialogue, in the form of holding open or closed roundtables and seminars. Such relations bring views closer together and can be very effective in resolving disputes. With this description, since the basis of interaction in these circles is not power but logic, this type of think tank diplomacy has been successful in many cases ^[6].

In this regard, the effectiveness of interactions in resolving disputes is achieved when they lead to bilateral and

multilateral agreements between the parties to the discussion. Although it seems that defensive diplomacy does not necessarily have to show itself in times of conflict, but should be considered an effective strategy in the course of international interactions. For example, in order to maintain regional power, a comprehensive political, economic, cultural and environmental perspective has a significant impact on structural and interactive coordination. Therefore, defensive diplomacy strives to preserve regional power, and this effort can be directed toward countering any emergence of regional and international crises ^[7].

Based on what has been said, one of the effective interactions at the regional level in order to protect the biosphere is environmental diplomacy. This framework can change the hard look at defensive diplomacy and consider it as an interactionist tool. Based on this and with this view, considering the goals of defensive diplomacy, this relationship can be explained

Table 3

Defensive Diplomacy's Important Objective	- Providing a ground for the supply of technology, equipment or defense weapons with consideration of environmental impact assessment to minimize contradiction - Playing a role in arms control and destructive weapons
Management of security areas and establishment of appropriate defense relations and interactions	- The process of improving security conditions in the region through constructive interactions - Promoting standards for defense products such as ships suitable for the sea with due regard to maritime and environmental regulations
Capacities in Proximity	- The convergence of environmental diplomacy and defense diplomacy in the context of mutual cooperation and reducing the risk of conflict - Biosecurity diplomacy and regional and international strategies

In this description, moving towards stability is a truth that the international community should not turn away from or deny. Therefore, the platforms for cooperation and multilateral interactions should be free from political and military conflicts. Although this is a necessity, it is not enough.

Human Rights and The Feasibility of Environmental Diplomacy

The world is undergoing rapid and comprehensive transformations. This process is sometimes disrupted by the self-interest and excessive demands of humankind, which exposes the threats to the biosphere. The international community must not remain silent and allow the danger to grow further. This is the concern of the public mind around the world that has driven us to strive and think about how to move the world towards togetherness. Therefore, it seems that in the near future, we should think more about the global environment, and this issue can only be realized through environmental diplomacy.

A change in attitude or approach towards human rights and environmental issues can be made possible in ten approaches ^[8]

Table 4

Approach 1	This human rights-based approach, for the first time, prior to the Stockholm Declaration, was based on the understanding of environmental protection as a precondition for the enjoyment of internationally guaranteed human rights, especially the rights to life and health.
Approach 2	This approach, which is based on the second generation of human rights, has been the most common approach in international environmental agreements since 1992. Environmental protection is considered a fundamental element of human rights, and some human rights documents have emphasized the need to achieve environmental protection as a goal of protecting human health. This approach is well illustrated in the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, adopted by the Rio de Janeiro Conference on Environment and Development in 1992. This approach largely treats the relationship between human rights and environmental protection as a procedural matter, such as in Principle 10 on information, public participation and access to effective judicial and administrative remedies. It emphasizes that environmental issues should be best addressed with the participatory behavior of all citizens, at the desired level.
Approach 3	The reference to the inseparable link between the right to a safe and healthy environment as an independent fundamental human right and human rights.
Approach 4	The relationship between the environment and human rights in the light of solidarity rights.
Approach 5	Constructive regional and international interactions within the framework of common human heritage and the balancing standard
Approach 6	Overcoming environmental hazards including climate change, pollution, environmental changes, and biodiversity
Approach 7	Understanding the geo-political and geo-strategic position at the regional and international level
Approach 8	The expediency and feasibility of peace and peacebuilding
Approach 9	Crowdsourcing
Approach 10	Generational rights, international human rights law, and sustainable development

This approach of thought shows that the two-way interaction between human rights and environmental diplomacy is timeless and spaceless, and takes place according to the appropriate situation and existing conditions. In fact, it is a kind of effective feasibility study that shows that there is a coherent relationship between the two.

International Interactions, a Platform for the Advancement of Environmental Diplomacy

In the surrounding world, peaceful coexistence has no alternative but peaceful interactions. These interactions are affected by various social, political, economic, cultural, and environmental dimensions, and these aspects are relatively interconnected and can be argued to be inseparable. However, we do not mean that inseparability is absolute and pure. In the global community, all these aspects are manifested through proper relations in the international arena, and its development is the product of diplomacy and, beyond that, environmental diplomacy, which plays a very valuable role in promoting the health of the global community. In this process, governance methods, security

and biological frameworks play a constructive role. This process clarifies the connecting indicators in the two axes of diplomacy and environment, the combined success of which depends on acting on shared commitments and being committed to the following aspects^[9]:

Firstly, diplomacy itself is derived from the science of politics and action in the field of international relations.

Second, from a social perspective, diplomacy requires the active role of various groups and public and private activists to achieve urban and civic stability.

Third, comprehensive diplomacy is effective in an environment where security plays a fundamental role, and this is not effective unless the surrounding environment is not involved in de-securitization, securitization, and insecurity.

Fourth, diplomacy affects development as well as the lucrative market for goods and services and stems from the role of the economy.

Fifth, if culture has no place in the orbit of diplomacy, the bitter consequences of this are evident in developing and underdeveloped societies.

Sixth, diplomacy without justice is indicative of the role-playing of false actors in the international community to escape the surrounding realities.

In any case, the basis of formal diplomacy in the international arena is in line with effective interactions.

Therefore, this important issue has always been a solution to many international problems, including environmental hazards. Although this process requires specific mechanisms in order to be effective and to promote international

cooperation, its development depends on regional and international priorities regarding bilateral and multilateral cooperation. Therefore, environmental diplomacy, as a combination of tools and methods to help resolve environmental and natural resource disputes, has a vital existence^[10].

With this description, environmental diplomacy monitors the various stages between sustainable peace and armed conflicts to help promote peace throughout the world and provides a framework for international interactions and a platform for common dialogue on environmental damage and natural resources.

Therefore, environmental diplomacy is a process that helps to achieve sustainable peace and natural resource protection.

Protection of the Global Environment and the Approach of Treaty Principles

The commitment of the international community and its adherence to it can be a solution to many environmental concerns. This should be taken into account by developed and developing countries. This is because, despite the proliferation of international environmental agreements, many environmental challenges have emerged. Now the question arises whether the defect is in the density and nature of the treaties or in the type of performance and treaty compliance.

It seems that part of this defect is due to the multiplicity and diversity of environmental agreements. This issue creates overlaps in responsibilities, requirements, goals, solutions, and strategies. Another part of the defect is in the lack of adherence to and implementation of treaties, which has actually caused the profit-seeking of countries to prevent environmental challenges from being properly controlled.

So, it is clear that new environmental challenges require coping and containment mechanisms^[11]. Throughout the development of international environmental law, it should be noted that effective strategies must be in place to observe its positive impact on how environmental

risks are mitigated. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the impact assessment of a treaty, the existence of national and international reward and punishment structures, the effectiveness of the treaty implementation system, and ultimately the position of commitments and the interactive approach. The impact of international environmental law in responding to new and emerging environmental challenges is partly dependent on our ability to escape the harmful influence of the broad concept of sovereignty in international law. It is clear that if we assume that international relations, international politics, and international law are only shaped by the nation-state.

However, it is not a nation-state that can solve and settle the environmental problems around it. Rather, overcoming these problems and challenges requires constructive international interactions in the form of specific international relations, which we can refer to as environmental diplomacy^[12]. In this regard, the scope of international efforts should be expanded and international environmental forums should make more effective decisions in this regard, and more useful consultations should take place between member states through environmental diplomacy.

In this context, a close examination of the role of public participation and access to information in achieving sustainable development and good environmental governance is also among the environmental issues of today. The close relationship between sustainable development and transparency and access to information plays an effective role in nurturing environmental outcomes. In this regard, the relationship between human rights and environmental protection, with a special focus on the rights of people, is also of great importance. In fact, the general right to a healthy environment is one of the most important foundations of international environmental law and the structural foundations of environmental and human rights discourse. It is here that international relations come into play and effective regional, international and global cooperation is considered and manifested. This process may take a formal or informal form, which is the special focus on environmental international interactions that takes place through environmental diplomacy.

The Approach of Non-Treaty Principles and Addressing Environmental Concerns

The existence of environmental crises has caused effective actions to be taken to address environmental concerns. In this regard, resorting to non-treaty instruments by the international community can have positive outcomes.

a. Joint Interactions and Effective Efforts

For the comprehensive protection of the environment, states call for an elevated level of cooperation to address emerging challenges. States await periodic global environmental meetings and the adoption of effective decisions regarding matters related to global environmental protection and the implementation of sustainable development. Through this, states want to stabilize international environmental governance and make international negotiations more effective. This is the same effective strategy of environmental diplomacy and its impact on international interactions. While the responsibility is common but differentiated, the world will no longer tolerate irresponsibility, and there is no doubt that irresponsibility

and non-compliance with this important international responsibility carries serious consequences^[13].

b. Crowdsourcing and Peacebuilding

It seems that the assistance of countries in realizing the principle of information dissemination and encouraging citizens to participate in environmental protection can turn many environmental concerns from challenges into opportunities. The presence of citizens in decision-making structures and making them concerned within the standard frameworks of cooperation with governments can lead to a significant growth of environmental social culture and adherence to environmental regulations and rights. With this description, cooperation frameworks can be used in the path of environmental diplomacy. These frameworks include crowdsourcing and creating the platform and foundation for public participation^[14]. Citizens, when they find a social identity, their genius emerges. Another framework is the peacebuilding discourse that curbs the state of hostility and, with respect to the principle of sovereignty, provides a platform for dialogue for environmental protection. With this description, both frameworks can impact long-term threats. However, these mechanisms should be fully monitored and move towards legal stability.

c. Policy Steps

Small steps are needed to create a legal framework to ensure the necessary environmental standards. However, it should be noted that there are international mechanisms and efforts to negotiate with due regard to the sovereign tools of states that realistically consider their national interests in protecting their sovereignty. From a global perspective, we have caused environmental degradation to deepen, and the path forward seems very difficult. International environmental problems that have spread beyond the details of individual problems have actually shifted the focus of criticism towards governments^[15].

In this regard, policy steps are necessary at the national, regional, and international levels to preserve environmental security and diplomacy. Therefore, it is emphasized that there should be a logical tool for answering scientific and technological questions and ensuring sustainable environmental balance. Furthermore, the concept of sustainable development and the framework for its development and promotion to a specific principle should be defined. In this regard, green diplomacy and multilateral efforts are aimed at achieving a common agreement or regime instead of effective restrictions and creating the necessary mechanism to ensure environmental protection.

Conclusion

The global system, in its course of evolution, requires human interaction, and this interaction also requires a suitable platform for moving forward. In this process, purposeful diplomacy can be the guarantor of the survival of human society and human life by preserving common interests with due regard to adherence to international commitments and compliance with mandatory rules. This purposefulness goes so far as to bring about global stability and peace. Today, environmental diplomacy, as one of the most important international and global issues, has a special perspective on the political, cultural, and legal dimensions of environmental issues. In this regard, the international community has taken a significant step towards sustainable

development by protecting the biosphere and at the same time promoting human quality of life with regard to human rights and human dignity based on justice, sovereignty, and law. This process is the product of the continuous and effective efforts of international actors in the course of conferences, meetings, and international summits and their outputs. Although environmental diplomacy is a completely serious process based on peace and soft law, it should not remain a low priority, as it can be considered a facilitator of the defensive diplomacy process in the region. This perspective truly illuminates the biosecurity diplomacy that is formed within the framework of the intersection of the two axes of environmental and defensive diplomacy. Ultimately, it must be acknowledged that despite the existence of formal and informal frameworks, the focus is largely on conventions and treaties, which due to their comprehensiveness, have not been able to be implemented in societies and have caused unintended international environmental impacts. In fact, this may be due to the inflexibility of formal environmental diplomacy. However, this inflexibility shows the wrong approach of the parties to diplomacy, because conversely, this process should take place in a completely flexible space.

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